

 REDRESS
RESTORING AND REBUILDING THE DEEP SEA

UAç
UNIVERSIDADE
DOS AÇORES

Summary

Field surveys were conducted in 2024 in Condor seamount with the aim of testing (1) the effectiveness of transplanting corals, sponges and hydroids using the badminton method and the Bio-liberator (BiLi) system, and (2) the ability of using the Azor drift-cam underwater video system to relocate and monitor the deployed organisms. The surveys were composed of two legs, one in August and another one in November 2024, with deployments of transplanted organisms made around 300 m depth on the same location over the seamount. Four deployments with the BiLi Release were performed, with a total of 82 specimens relocated, and 6 dives with the Azor drift-cam, which allowed 19 specimens to be revisited.

Dates:

Leg 1: 8th to 9th August 2024

Leg 2: 29th October 2024

Vessel

RV Águas Vivas (IMAR, Universidade do Açores)

Scientific team

Marina Carreiro-Silva, Gal-la Edery, António Godinho, Carlos Dominguez-Carrió, Inês Bruno

Figure 1. Location of the restoration site. Yellow stars indicate the location of the coral deployments. Colour lines indicate the path over the seabed performed with the Azor drift-cam in the different transects.

Table 1. Metadata of the different deployments made during the REDRESS surveys done in 2024.

Leg	Instrument	Station	Date	Time		Start at bottom		End at bottom	
				At water	Off-water	Latitude (deg)	Longitude (deg)	Latitude (deg)	Longitude (deg)
1	BiLi	REDRESS_2024_D001	08/08/24	10:18:39	-	38.5170	-28.9672	-	-
1	BiLi	REDRESS_2024_D002	08/08/24	11:26:18	-	38.5169	-28.9673	-	-
1	BiLi	REDRESS_2024_D003	08/08/24	11:57:49	-	38.5168	-28.9673	-	-
1	Azor drift-cam	REDRESS_2024_St001	09/08/24	09:23:06	09:58:30	38.5176	-28.9670	38.5155	-28.9685
1	Azor drift-cam	REDRESS_2024_St002	09/08/24	10:05:02	10:48:32	38.5173	-28.9671	38.5157	-28.9682
1	Azor drift-cam	REDRESS_2024_St003	09/08/24	11:13:00	12:04:36	38.5170	-28.9672	38.5143	-28.9709
1	Azor drift-cam	REDRESS_2024_St004	09/08/24	12:16:30	12:47:34	38.5170	-28.9672	38.5173	-28.9686
1	Azor drift-cam	REDRESS_2024_St005	09/08/24	13:41:28	14:13:57	38.5171	-28.9675	38.5194	-28.9695
1	Azor drift-cam	REDRESS_2024_St006	09/08/24	14:21:35	14:47:38	38.5173	-28.9665	38.5187	-28.9670
2	BiLi	REDRESS_2024_St007	29/10/24	12:32:00	-	38.5183	-28.9676	-	-

Leg 1

Scientific team in Leg 1: Marina Carreiro-Silva, Gal-la Ederly, António Godinho, Carlos Dominguez-Carrió, Inês Bruno.

Preparation of the organisms for transplantation

Between the months of April and July 2024, **UAc** and **IMAR** teams obtained cold-water corals, sponges and hydroids accidentally caught as bycatch during long-line fisheries surveys on board RV Arquipélago. All organisms were maintained onboard in cooler boxes with chilled seawater and upon arrival to shore they were transferred to the DeepSeaLab facilities where they were fragmented and maintained in aquaria.

Organisms were prepared for transplantation using the Badminton method as described in Montseny et al. (2020). Accordingly, we selected cobbles with a size of approximately 15 x 10 cm, and a weight range between 0.5-2 kg. Cobbles were sterilized with 10% bleach during 3-4 h, dried and painted with white acrylic paint (KOBY). The code of each organism was written on the cobble with a permanent marker. Specimens were photographed in the lab to have a record of their status before deployment (Figure 2).

Figure 2. (Top) Photographing the organisms to be transplanted. (Bottom) Examples of the sponge *Phakellia ventillabrum* and cold-water coral *Dentomuricea* aff. *meteor* after being mounted in cobbles.

One day before the field survey, two isothermal tanks of 350 L, a chiller (HAILEA HC1000A), the BiLi-Release, rope, and a USBL device and related equipment were placed in the RV Águas Vivas for the maintenance and transportation of the organisms to be transplanted. Each of the two tanks was filled with 250 L of seawater collected outside Horta's harbour to avoid contaminants and other substances that could be present in the harbour's water. Seawater inside the tanks was refrigerated to the target temperature (15 °C) using a chiller, while organisms were transported from the DeepSeaLab facilities to the vessel inside coolers with chilled seawater. Organisms were kept in the tanks on board of the vessel overnight.

Figure 3. Set up of the tanks with the BiLi and the organisms to be transplanted on board of RV Águas Vivas.

8th August 2024

We left Horta harbour at 7:20 am and arrived to the restoration site at 9:30 am. The work was performed between 9:30 am and 1:00 pm. We returned to the harbour at 3:00 pm. Three deployments were performed with 62 organisms: 21 in the first deployment, 20 in the second, and 21 in the third. Unfortunately, the deployments did not go as expected, and all organisms were released from surface after the BiLi released opened accidentally. The target location for the deployments was 38° 31.039' N - 28° 58.0162' W, over the summit of Condor seamount with a bottom depth of 300 m.

Figure 4. Images of the deployments made with the BiLi system on board of RV Águas Vivas during Leg 1.

BiLi deployment 1. The first set of organisms deployed (Table 2) were already inside the BiLi system at the time of arrival, since it was placed inside one of the tanks. The BiLi system consisted of a cage equipped with a camera placed inside a pressure housing and LED lights, and a cylinder containing external batteries attached to the deployment rope that lowered the cage from the vessel. For this first deployment trial, we used a ballast stone with 15 kg that was kept hanging from the boat until the BiLi

was ready to be lowered in the water column. The BiLi system was transferred to the side of the boat manually by two people, sided with the opening mechanism facing the boat. This made the mechanism to get stuck on the side of the boat causing the device to open at the surface and release the organisms.

BiLi deployment 2. For the second deployment we made a few modifications on the BiLi system to improve the execution. The ballast stone was changed for a lighter one of 6 kg. BiLi was partly supported by a second rope on the ship’s deck to help move it easily. We placed the BiLi system inside the second tank and placed the organisms for the second deployment in the cage (Table 2). The ballast stone was placed in the water, kept hanging from the boat as the previous deployment. The BiLi was transferred to the side of the boat by two people, while a third person elevating the rope to control the release system once the BiLi was entering the water to start its descent slowly. Unfortunately, when the BiLi was placed in the water, the security mechanism that maintain the cage closed was released, making the equipment to open a few meters from the surface and releasing all the organisms.

BiLi deployment 3. For the third deployment, additional changes were made to the BiLi for a better execution. The security mechanism was changed for a non-elastic one, the ballast stone was change to 15 kg, and a little rope was placed to increase the strength and reduce the swinging of the device, which prevented the mechanism from opening before reaching the seafloor. The third batch of organisms (Table 2) was placed inside the BiLi, and the equipment was lowered in the water column. When we noticed that the equipment had reached the seafloor by the reduction of tension on the cable, the equipment was brought back to the vessel with the help of a hauler. However, when the BiLi reached the surface, we realised that the cage had not opened, and the organisms were still inside. Because of this malfunctioning and to avoid exposure of the organisms to the air, we decided to release the organisms from the surface, opening the cage manually. The analysis of the video footage taken inside the cage revealed that the cause for the malfunction was the entanglement of cylinders containing the batteries with the ropes.

Table 2. Number and taxa of the organisms that were transplanted in each deployment.

BiLi deployment 1		BiLi deployment 2		BiLi deployment 3	
190	Hydrozoa	215	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>	213.1	<i>Acanthogorgia</i> sp.
195	<i>Acanthogorgia</i> sp.	231	<i>Phakellia ventilabrum</i>	170B	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>
219.3	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	222E	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	212.2	<i>Acanthogorgia</i> sp.
222A2	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	234A	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>	221E	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>
219.2	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	185	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>	97B	<i>Lytocarpia myriophyllum</i>
140.1	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>	167E	Porifera	135A	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
196	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>	167B	Porifera	210	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
213.2	<i>Acanthogorgia</i> sp.	166	Hydrozoa	170A	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>
208B	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>	222F	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	222E2	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>
219.1	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	170C	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>	126	<i>Ircinia dendroides</i>
222B3	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	96A	<i>Acanthogorgia</i> sp.	227	<i>Corallium</i> sp.
212.1	<i>Acanthogorgia</i> sp.	211	<i>Acanthogorgia</i> sp.	218.2	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>
214A	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>	100	<i>Raspailia humilis</i>	218.1	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>
214B	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>	194	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>	189	<i>Polyplumaria flabellata</i>
212.3	<i>Acanthogorgia</i> sp.	221G	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	96B	<i>Acanthogorgia</i> sp.
161	<i>Phakellia ventilabrum</i>	240	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>	140	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
220A1	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	186	<i>Phakellia ventilabrum</i>	167C	<i>Ircinia dendroides</i>
221F	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	254	<i>Polyplumaria flabellata</i>	253	<i>Polyplumaria flabellata</i>
214C	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>	221A4	<i>Dentomuricea</i> aff <i>meteor</i>	252	<i>Polyplumaria flabellata</i>
144	<i>Lytocarpia myriophyllum</i>	244	Hydrozoa	162	<i>Lytocarpia myriophyllum</i>
174	<i>Phakellia ventilabrum</i>			167A	Porifera
Total: 21		Total: 20		Total: 21	

9th August 2024

We revisited the site where the organisms were deployed with the Azor drift-cam with the objective of testing the ability of the Azor drift-cam to relocate and monitor the deployed organisms. Specifically, we aimed to assess if the organisms with the cobbles had successfully landed at the seafloor in an upright position, whether they had detached from the cobbles, and what was their dispersion range. Six dives and 237 minutes of immersion were undertaken with the Azor drift-cam. The deployment area was successfully located during the second and third dives.

Figure 5. Depth profiles and temperature measurements of Dives 2 and 3, in which transplanted corals were recorded by the Azor drift-cam. Depth profile is indicated with the orange line and temperature with the blue line.

Figure 6. Images of some of the organisms relocated that were filmed during Dive 2

Figure 7. Images of some of the organisms relocated that were filmed during Dive 3.

Summary of organisms observed in the images:

- Specimens recorded during Dive 2: 144, 208B, 196, 190, 214C (from deployment 1).
- Specimens recorded during dive 3: 185, 215, 240, 167B, 254, 186, 231, 211, 140, 221G, 222E, 170A, 234A (from deployment 2 and 3). One of the organisms from the species *Dentomuricea* aff. *meteor* detached from the cobble during the deployment (222E2).

Leg 2

Scientific team in Leg 2: António Godinho, Inês Bruno, Gal·la Edery.

Preparation of the field survey

Because of the problems identified with opening of the BiLi device, we made some modifications to the device prior to the 2nd leg to improve the execution: (1) the top part of the equipment was covered with a mesh to prevent the cylinder to enter the cage while lowering the device into the water column; (2) the opening mechanism was modified to prevent the opening of the cage before reaching the seafloor.

In addition, we replaced the USBL system with another positioning system that provided more accurate data.

28th October 2024

One isothermic tank with the organisms to be transplanted, a chiller (HAILEA HC1000A), the BiLi-Release device, rope, and USBL system and related equipment, were placed in the RV Águas Vivas the day before the field survey, similarly to what was done for Leg 1 (see details above).

29th October 2024

We left the Horta harbour at 8:15 am and arrived to the deployment area at 10:15 am. The work was performed between 10:15 am and 1:00 pm. We returned to the harbour at 3:00 pm. We started by testing the drift of the boat by deploying only the USBL. After that, we proceeded with the deployment of the BiLi device with the organisms to be transplanted (D004). The deployment was performed with 20 organisms (

Table 3. Number and taxa of the organisms that were transplanted in deployment 4.

Table 3). The target location for the deployment was 38° 31.039' N - 28° 58.016' W.

BiLi deployment 4.

Before the deployment, we checked that the USBL system was working properly and responding. A ballast stone with the USBL system was dropped from the vessel. Initially, we had some problems with the connection of the USBL software with the GPS. When the problem was solved, we let the USBL drift for a while to check if it was responding and functioning well. While the USBL was being tested, the captain was checking the drift of the boat to estimate the relative position for the deployment.

For the deployment, we used a ballast stone with 15 kg. The deployment of the Bili was successful, with the cage opening and releasing the organisms close to the seafloor, as we could confirm on the video recordings.

Figure 8. Images of the organisms inside the BiLi and being released close to the seafloor.

Table 3. Number and taxa of the organisms that were transplanted in deployment 4.

Deployment 4	
176	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
148	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
33.1B	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>
150	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
198A	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
61	Hydrozoa
150Gr	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
147	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
145	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
211A	<i>Dentomuricea aff. meteor</i>
58.3	<i>Acanthogorgia armata</i>
221B2	<i>Dentomuricea aff. meteor</i>
136C	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
33.1A	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>
199	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
183	<i>Viminella flagellum</i>
50B	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>
50A	<i>Callogorgia verticillata</i>
58.2	<i>Acanthogorgia armata</i>
54	<i>Dentomuricea aff. meteor</i>
Total: 20	

Transplanted organisms will be revisited in the summer of 2025 with the Azor drift-cam to assess their survival over time.

References

Montseny M, Linares C, Viladrich N, Capdevila P, Ambroso S, Díaz D, Gili JM, Gori A (2020). A new large-scale and cost-effective restoration method to cold-water coral gardens. *Aquatic Conservation: Marine and Fresh Water Ecosystems* 30:5, 977-987. <https://doi.org/10.1002/aqc.3303>